

uPcycle

A Framework for Gender Mainstreaming in Sustainable Phosphorus Management for Nature Recovery

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this document

This framework document serves as a resource for stakeholders involved in projects and programmes aimed at achieving sustainable phosphorus cycles in lake catchments, whether at the national or subnational level. However, the overarching processes described are also relevant to a range of projects within environmental management and beyond. The document provides a suggested framework to integrate gender mainstreaming measures at the project planning stage, in addition to implementation and monitoring. This framework outlines established language, the gender mainstreaming process, recommended indicators as well as useful questions to consider at the planning stage.

By integrating gender considerations into these initiatives, this document supports project managers in designing projects/programmes that consider the diverse needs, priorities, and perspectives of individuals, regardless of gender. By following the guidance outlined within, project planners, policymakers, and implementers can enhance the effectiveness and inclusivity of their efforts, leading to more sustainable outcomes. Ultimately, the utilisation of the framework will help support more equitable and resilient phosphorus management practices that benefit both ecosystems and communities, paving the way for a more sustainable future for all.

The phosphorus challenge

Unsustainable phosphorus use has pushed global food security further beyond reach and is leaving a legacy of polluted freshwaters around the world (Brownlie et al., 2021). If phosphorus emissions to our lakes are not reduced in the coming years, then the environmental and socio-economic impacts are predicted to be irreversible (Carpenter & Bennett, 2011). There is currently no global policy on sustainable phosphorus use (Brownlie et al., 2022a).

Momentum to address global concerns over unsustainable phosphorus is building, reflecting a growing awareness of its detrimental impacts on food security and freshwater ecosystems worldwide (Brownlie et al., 2022b). In response to this urgent issue, stakeholders are coming together to address phosphorus emissions and their environmental consequences, particularly in lakes and aquatic ecosystems (WWQA Ecosystems, 2023).

2. Phosphorus and Gender

Phosphorus and Gender

While the relationship between phosphorus and gender equality may not appear direct, phosphorus, as both an agricultural nutrient and a pollutant, is a crucial component in both global food security and water security, in which there are obvious gender disparities (Figure 1).

Figure 1. *Examples of gender disparities relating to food security and water security (FAO, 2019; UNICEF, 2023; World Bank, 2012).*

Food Security

Globally, women are pivotal in food production and security. Notably, 60% of the undernourished population consists of women and girls (WFP, 2015), residing mostly in Asia, Africa, Latin America and the Caribbean (FAO, 2019). Women also represent 43% of the agricultural labour force in the developing world, rising to 50% in Asia and sub-Saharan Africa (FAO, 2014). These women produce food for both household and community consumption and, compared to men, tend to allocate a larger portion of their income to food, health, and education for their children. By increasing agricultural productivity and empowering women economically, specifically by involving them in decision-making regarding their income and access to credit, food security can be significantly improved. This can lead to greater diversity and consumption of food, enhancing the nutritional status of household members (Kruse, 2019; FAO, 2020).

Gender-based discrimination, which manifests through laws, social norms, practices, and the denial of women's rights, for example, is a major contributor to poverty and food and nutrition insecurity (Mukhovi, 2009; Kruse, 2019). In several countries, women lack land rights (Doss, 2001; Hillenbrand et al., 2015), and have limited access to credit to improve productivity. Together with institutional and normative barriers, these overlapping constraints restrict their access to information, extension services, and technologies, such as hybrid seeds and fertiliser and thus hinder agricultural efficiency and productivity (Mukhovi, 2009). Thus, contributions towards environmentally sustainable agricultural practices, such as sustainable phosphorus management, may also be hindered. Access to education is equally vital for women, with many women employed as wage agricultural workers disproportionately represented in the unskilled labour force due to lower educational levels. They receive lower salaries, often calculated on a piece-rate basis, and frequently work under informal, temporary contracts (De Schutter, 2012; FAO, 2020).

Water Security

Access to water is characterised by inequalities, depending on natural water availability and the respective socio-political context. As a nexus exists among water, land, and food security, access to water is also influenced by gender-differentiated roles and responsibilities, presenting similar barriers to food security. In rural and agricultural communities, women and girls are primarily responsible for collecting water for domestic use (Figure 1) (Dickin and Caretta, 2022; Tantoh et al., 2021). Limited access to safe water and the restricted formal rights on resource management worsen the vulnerabilities faced by women in these areas, including health risks (Tantoh et al., 2021). Safe water collection has numerous harmful effects on women and girls, including long-term injuries (Geere et al., 2018; Robson et al., 2013), exposure to conflicts and different types of violence including gender violence (Nunbogu and Elliott, 2021), and a discouragement from participating in other important activities, such as education, due to the time-consuming nature of water collection (Robson et al., 2013). Moreover, in the context of agricultural production, women often have unequal participation in management and governance roles. This is reflected in their underrepresentation in water user associations and their limited involvement in decision-making related to irrigation management (Imburgia et al., 2021; UN Women, 2024), which ultimately restricts advancements in farming practices which in turn effects local water quality and water security.

The importance of gender-responsive planning in phosphorus management

Incorporating gender mainstreaming practices into projects and programmes aims to integrate considerations for genders across different social, economic and geographic demographics in both planning and implementation (Prasetyo et al., 2023). Acknowledging the importance of gender equality and women's rights in sustainable phosphorus management is crucial from a human rights standpoint (Agarwal, 2018). Furthermore, research indicates that initiatives aiming to achieve more sustainable use of agricultural nutrients will achieve greater efficiency and efficacy by considering gender equality and incorporating gender equity measures. This integration has the potential to

benefit various areas such as food security, water security, and sustainable agriculture (Adam et al., 2021; Farnworth et al., 2017; Leslie et al., 2019; Meinzen-Dick et al., 2014).

Different genders play varied roles and possess distinct priorities and requirements concerning the ecosystem services offered by lakes and their catchment areas, all of which contribute to the welfare of their households and communities. Implementing a gender-responsive approach can expand the scope of many projects. In doing so, practitioners will benefit from a broader knowledge base and will increase the equity of benefits from their actions (Broeckhoven & Cliquet, 2015). Integration of gender considerations tends to generate broader local buy-in and can incentivise all to contribute to restoration efforts, providing greater opportunities for enhanced well-being, as well as chances for the long-term sustainability of freshwater restoration efforts (Ahmed, 2005; Lester & Rosten, 2020).

In contrast, failing to engage with women or acknowledge their contributions to the subject area carries inherent risks to the efficacy of a project. (Sinharoy & Caruso, 2019). Initiatives in aquatic resources management that overlook gender considerations have worsened gender disparities and, in some cases, restricted women's access to water and resources, diminished their influence and autonomy, and increased their workload (Ahmed, 2005; Freitas et al., 2020). Adopting gender-transformative approaches can enhance individual capacities, challenge existing gender norms, and address the power inequalities both women and men experience. This approach promotes women's social and political influence, contributing to a more equitable society (FAO, 2020).

The following sections develop a framework through which gender considerations can be integrated into existing and emerging sustainable phosphorus programmes in lake catchments, relevant for both national and subnational efforts.

3. Gender Mainstreaming

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Gender Mainstreaming

The Building Blocks of the Framework: defining gender, gender inclusivity and gender mainstreaming

In designing gender-inclusive and socially inclusive programmes, it is crucial to establish a common understanding of key terms such as gender, gender equality, gender equity, gender mainstreaming, and gender inclusivity. While definitions of these terms are subject to ongoing refinement, this document adopts the following definitions to guide our discussion and implementation of gender-responsive initiatives.

Gender: Refers to the socially constructed roles, behaviours, activities, and attributes that a given society considers appropriate for different genders. It encompasses a wide range of characteristics, including but not limited to biological sex (male, female, intersex), gender identity (one's internal sense of their gender), gender expression (how one presents their gender to others), and social roles and expectations associated with gender.

We highlight that gender is not solely determined by biology; it is shaped by cultural, social, and environmental factors. Different societies have different understandings of gender, and these perceptions can change over time. Gender norms and expectations can influence various aspects of life, including access to resources, opportunities, and social status. Understanding gender is essential for addressing inequalities and promoting diversity and inclusion in society. While this document often focuses on women's involvement and engagement, the framework is designed to be inclusive of all genders.

Gender Equality: This means ensuring all genders have equal access to rights and opportunities.

Gender Equity: This describes the process of addressing and compensating for gender-based differences and disadvantages to ensure equitable treatment. Gender equity leads to gender equality (UNFPA, 2005).

Gender Responsive: This describes the approach in which considerations are made for gender norms to address the associated inequalities, beyond awareness raising (De Groot, 2018).

Gender Mainstreaming: This is a strategy for integrating gender perspectives into all stages of policy-making, planning, implementation, and monitoring. It involves analysing the implications of any planned action on different genders and taking proactive steps to promote gender equality and address gender disparities.

How do we gender mainstream?

Gender mainstreaming, described above, involves evaluating the potential impacts on different genders at the outset of any planned action, whether it be legislation, policies, or programmes across various domains and levels. This approach acknowledges that individuals of different genders have diverse needs and may be affected differently by development initiatives. It recognises the disparities in access to information and opportunities among genders and aims to design projects in a way that ensures equal benefits for all genders while avoiding inadvertent disadvantages or neglect. Gender mainstreaming is not a standalone activity but an integral part of the project or policy cycle, aimed at enhancing efficiency and effectiveness. It entails incorporating gender considerations into all stages of planning, implementation and monitoring, rather than being an additional component.

While achieving gender mainstreaming may be a gradual process, it is an ongoing endeavour to continuously improve and address gender inequities. Practical gender mainstreaming involves systematically asking pertinent questions to ensure that no gender is overlooked and that resources are allocated where they are most needed.

Figure 2. *Gender mainstreaming key steps and outcomes.*

Gender mainstreaming involves several key steps to ensure that the needs and perspectives of all genders are considered and addressed effectively (Figure 2.). At a broad scale, these steps will likely include:

Ensuring stakeholder gender representation: Determine the gender demographics expected to be impacted by the initiative/project to better understand their specific challenges and strive for representation within stakeholder groups. Ideally, this would also consider the different intersections of gender, taking age, ethnicity and other demographic information into account.

Conducting Gender Analysis: Collect gender-disaggregated data and analyse it to identify who holds formal and informal power, makes decisions, controls resources, and benefits within the given context. This analysis helps reveal disparities and inequalities between genders.

Identifying Gender Equality Issues and Gaps: Through data analysis and consultations with representatives of all genders, identify both obvious and subtle gender disparities and gaps in equality. This process helps in accurately diagnosing the problems and understanding the needs of different genders.

Designing Projects to Address Gender Issues: Develop projects and initiatives that aim to address the identified gender disparities. Consider various avenues for change, including legal, policy, cultural, and service-related interventions, tailored to the specific needs and contexts of different genders. Examine for possible unintended negative consequences of proposed interventions and mitigate where possible.

By following these steps, organisations and policymakers can effectively mainstream gender considerations into their projects and policies, ensuring their efforts to benefit all genders equally and contribute to greater gender equality.

Structuring indicators within a Framework

It is advisable to organise indicators within a structured framework to comprehensively cover various aspects of gender responsiveness within the sustainable phosphorus management programme. Among various conceptual models, the Reach-Benefit-Empower-Transform (RBET) framework, developed by CGIAR (Gonzales et al, 2024) is recommended due to its compatibility with monitoring gender mainstreaming efforts. Ideally, the monitoring system should encompass indicators that capture all four elements of this framework—reach, benefit, empower, and transform (Figure 3). This ensures a holistic approach to monitoring gender mainstreaming efforts and facilitates effective evaluation of the programme’s impact on gender equality in sustainable phosphorus management planning.

	REACH	BENEFIT	EMPOWER	TRANSFORM
OBJECTIVE	To achieve gender inclusive representation in sustainable phosphorus management initiatives.	Provide equitable access to capacity building and knowledge sharing across all stakeholder groups.	Enhance women's participation and role in decision-making processes	Contribute to long-term change by ensuring project outputs address gender inequities and raising awareness of the importance on considering gender in sustainable phosphorus initiatives.
STRATEGY	Mitigate barriers to women and members of minority groups participating in workshops and pre-establish gender representation objectives by integrating gender mainstreaming objectives into the results framework.	Consider gender differences and needs when planning workshops or training opportunities. Strive for gender equity by addressing and compensating for gendered disadvantages.	Addressing gender gaps in decision-making, leadership and management roles. Encouraging and reinforcing women's agency in these roles as well as in community spaces.	Improve internal and external understanding of the intricacies and importance of gender considerations by raising awareness and providing training opportunities.
INDICATORS	Percentage of different genders of different age-groups and ethnicities participating in a project workshop, meeting or field visit. Figures will be established from participants' self-report and will be evaluated throughout the project lifecycle.	Gender-disaggregated data collected on workshop and training outcomes and attendance (e.g. increased confidence and skills gained).	Decisions made and responsibilities demonstrated by women throughout the project. Gender representation in decision making roles and working groups.	A shift in attitudes and an enhanced effort placed on implementing gender mainstreaming demonstrated in future project planning.

Figure 3. Example of a structured indicator framework to aid the implementation and monitoring of gender mainstreaming efforts in sustainable phosphorus projects and programmes. Based on the RBET framework developed by CGLAR (Gonzales, et al., 2024).

4. A Useful Checklist to Support Gender Mainstreaming

SHOUT OUTS
JASON
IN HERGANCE
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SHOUT OUTS
ELOISE
WEBSITE TEMPLATES
& QUALITY

SHOUT OUTS
JANUARY
IN HERGANCE
in charge

SHOUT OUTS
ELOISE
WEBSITE TEMPLATES
& QUALITY

A useful checklist to support gender mainstreaming

When integrating gender mainstreaming measures into sustainable phosphorus management programmes, the following questions may be considered.

Does the programme articulate clear monitoring objectives that acknowledge the importance of gender equality?

For sustainable phosphorus management planning, the monitoring objectives of the programme could prioritise gender equality and outline strategies to address gender disparities effectively. These objectives will require further refinement, potentially through additional research and analysis to identify specific gender gaps. Engaging in participatory action research involving people of different genders, ages, and ethnicities, including indigenous communities, can offer valuable insights into the nuances of the sustainable phosphorus management programme, fostering reflection and co-learning opportunities.

Integrating a baseline gender analysis can help understand existing gender disparities, within regions and sectors, ensuring interventions are targeted and contextually relevant.

Examples of gender mainstreaming monitoring objectives include:

- Understanding the diverse contributions of different genders, and intersections (e.g. ethnicity, age and disability), to phosphorus management efforts and assessing whether these initiatives enhance their livelihoods and income.
- Striving for equal gender representation throughout the project, for example, setting a key performance indicator of 50% of workshop participants to be women, and addressing associated inequities in order to meet this goal. Equal opportunities for genders to influence decisions, lead discussions, and shape outcomes. Additionally considering the intersections of gender in this objectives will help to ensure interventions address unique needs of different groups.
- Monitoring progress towards inclusion of gender-responsive targets in national, regional, and international phosphorus management strategies, and identifying opportunities for enhancing implementation.
- Investigating how ecosystem degradation impacts the livelihoods and well-being of different demographic groups by diminishing access to essential resources such as foods (derived from both aquaculture and terrestrial agriculture), water and biodiversity. Additionally, identifying priority needs for these groups in relation to sustainable phosphorus management initiatives is crucial.

By incorporating gender mainstreaming monitoring objectives, sustainable phosphorus management programmes can ensure inclusivity and effectiveness, thereby maximising their positive impacts on both the environment and communities.

Have specific objectives and targets for gender mainstreaming within the project/programme been set?

Have specific objectives and targets for gender mainstreaming within the sustainable phosphorus management planning been established? Objectives pertaining to gender equality and responsiveness within the programme should be clearly defined, with related targets being specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART). Typically, objectives would encompass key elements of gender equality, such as participation, benefit-sharing, and empowerment.

These monitoring objectives should align with governmental directives and legislation aimed at promoting gender equality, such as constitutional provisions, anti-discrimination acts, and gender equality policies. Furthermore, the programme should integrate a gender perspective into its monitoring framework, ensuring that data collection, analysis, and reporting mechanisms are sensitive to gender dynamics and disparities.

Examples of specific gender mainstreaming monitoring objectives may include:

- Enhancing access to phosphorus management-related knowledge, education, and training opportunities for women, and minorities
- Increasing employment opportunities in sustainable phosphorus management for women, youth, elderly individuals, and people with disabilities.
- Designing phosphorus management technologies and monitoring mechanisms that are relevant and accessible to women, youth, elderly individuals, and people with disabilities.
- Improving access to land rights for women, youth, elderly individuals, and people with disabilities.
- Enhancing access to microcredit and loans linked to phosphorus management for women, youth, elderly individuals, and people with disabilities.
- Increasing the participation of women, youth, elderly individuals, and people with disabilities in decision-making related to phosphorus management.
- Ensuring project recommendations consider effects on different genders and strive to incorporate gender responsiveness.

By setting clear and targeted gender mainstreaming objectives, sustainable phosphorus management planning can ensure gender responsiveness, fostering participation and empowerment among diverse demographic groups. Additionally, allocating a specific budget for gender-mainstreaming activities

ensures that these objectives can be implemented effectively and sustained over time

Have qualitative and quantitative methods been combined effectively?

To ensure comprehensive monitoring outcomes, it is advisable to integrate both qualitative and quantitative methods. Quantitative measurements, such as improvements in income or the number of women participating in training or on advisory boards, should be complemented with qualitative information (e.g. reports of involvement in decision-making or contributions from different genders) to contextualise numerical data and understand the pathways leading to observed changes. This combined approach provides a nuanced understanding of programme impacts and informs strategies for improvement.

Have efforts been made to fully involve women throughout the different facets of the project/programme to enhance their capacity?

Special efforts should be made to actively involve women throughout the project at all levels to promote meaningful participation in all stages of the project, including decision-making. It is essential to address social norms and overcome barriers to women's participation. While women may possess inherent knowledge relevant to the project or programme's objectives due to their daily experiences, their capacity for contributing to outputs may require enhancement. Therefore, efforts to integrate gender considerations should focus on practical capacity development to ensure women are not only represented through attendance but by meaningful participation as well. It may be that this aspect benefits from providing multiple avenues for participation, e.g. the option, where appropriate, for women to share perspectives through 1:1s, single gender focus groups or follow-up surveys in addition to mixed focus groups where women may feel less empowered to participate.

Efforts may also be made to strengthen the capacity of marginalised groups such as providing opportunities for increasing technical knowledge and leadership training, for example, to enhance empowerment in influencing decision-making processes.

Have ethical considerations for gender reporting been appropriately assessed and applied?

With any human research, especially one collecting sensitive information such as gender and ethnicity, it is important to consider ethics at the planning stage. Depending on the country in which the project is taking place, it is often advised to seek formal ethical approval from a Research Ethics Committee. Ensuring the informed consent of participants is crucial as well as including measures to anonymise personal data, minimise the requirement of personal data as well as ensure secure storage and disposal. It is advised to seek clarity on data protection regulations that apply to the region where the project/programme is operating.

Is the gender mainstreaming monitoring system transparent in communicating results?

Transparency is essential in the monitoring system to communicate progress, achievements, and impacts related to specific gender mainstreaming objectives. The system should provide evidence of who benefits from phosphorus management interventions and how they benefit through periodic assessments. Additionally, figures on the gender representation of the project's decision-making teams should be made available. Transparent reporting enhances accountability and facilitates informed decision-making.

Are gender mainstreaming monitoring results being utilised to adapt management and improve implementation?

The monitoring system should serve as an objective tool to evaluate progress and guide adaptive management. Data collection should be conducted systematically and independently to avoid bias, including gender bias. Monitoring results can inform investment opportunities for donors and partners to allocate resources and technical capacity to the programme. A robust monitoring system with accurate results fosters trust and encourages additional investments for programme scaling. Moreover, the system helps identify the specific needs of women and marginalised groups in the context of sustainable phosphorus management.

Are lessons learned from monitoring gender mainstreaming being disseminated?

Experiences and lessons learned from monitoring gender mainstreaming can be documented and shared widely to facilitate collective learning and inspire replication. Monitoring results can be made publicly accessible and disseminated strategically at international, national, and subnational levels to maximise impact and inform policy and practice.

Has the broader enabling environment been considered?

Consideration of the broader enabling environment is crucial to safeguarding women's rights and interests in phosphorus management efforts. Political support at the highest level is necessary to ensure equitable benefits for all stakeholders. The phosphorus management programme can play a transformative role in influencing the enabling environment by advocating with policymakers and sharing experiences and lessons learned effectively.

Is the project raising awareness about gender internally as well as externally?

An effective method of helping to achieve gender equality is through internal and external engagement activities. These may be in the form of workshops, presentations, videos or reports, but all with the common aim of raising awareness on the importance of gender equality and why it is essential to furthering sustainable phosphorus management.

Guidance to define and track gender mainstreaming indicators.

Choosing suitable indicators to monitor gender mainstreaming efforts in any sustainable phosphorus management planning can be one of the most challenging tasks. Several key considerations for indicator selection relevant to gender mainstreaming include:

Opting for socioeconomic indicators that facilitate integrated, consistent, realistic, and regular monitoring of the sustainable phosphorus management programme. These indicators can adhere to the SMART criteria - specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound.

Considering the dual nature of indicators. For instance, while a high level of women's participation in phosphorus management activities may seem positive, it could also indicate heavier workloads for women due to additional household responsibilities.

When using indicators that require self-report methods or participant involvement, the project may consider also striving to minimise the burden of such indicators to reduce attrition and reduce ethical implications associated with sensitive personal data.

Identifying indicators utilised in related monitoring frameworks or systems to ensure comparability, consistency, and reliability across different levels of implementation - be it project, national, regional, or global. Efforts can be made to align selected indicators with reporting commitments under conventions such as the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the Ramsar Convention, and the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD), among others.

By integrating these indicators into long-term monitoring and embedding gender mainstreaming practices into the project's plan, the project/programme can evaluate the enduring impact of its interventions on livelihoods, decision-making, and environmental outcomes, ensuring benefits continue beyond the programme lifecycle.

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6. Useful resources

UNIDO (2015): Guide on Gender Mainstreaming: Environmental Management Projects. https://www.unido.org/sites/default/files/2015-02/Gender_Environmental_Management_Projects_0.pdf

GEF (2018): Guidance to Advance Gender Equality in GEF projects and programmes. https://www.thegef.org/sites/default/files/council-meeting-documents/EN_GEF.C.54.Inf_.05_Guidance_Gender.pdf

UNDP (2016): How to Conduct a Gender Analysis. https://info.undp.org/sites/bpps/SES_Toolkit/SES%20Document%20Library/Uploaded%20October%202016/UNDP%20Guidance%20Note%20how%20to%20conduct%20a%20gender%20analysis.pdf

UNEP (2017): Gender and Environment: Support Kit for UN Environment Staff. https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/25348/Gender_Environment_Kit.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y

FAO Policy on Gender Equality 2020-2030: <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/a75d575e-9f7e-45ad-afd9-a2cbfda37ad7/content#:~:text=FAO's%20commitment%20to%20promote%20gender,All%20Forms%20of%20Discrimination%20against>